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project

D4.4: Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis

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Deliverable Review and Approval

The individuals listed below are not directly involved in the preparation of this deliverable and will review the present document.

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Executive summary

One of the core goals of Project O is to demonstrate the efficacy of adopting water reuse technologies to shift towards a circular economy for long-term, sustainable water management. While globally water reuse is of great interest to contrast the projected increase in global and local water demands, water loops have the potential to become an essential component of integrated water management strategies in water-stressed regions. Project O Work Package 4 targets the design, development, and testing of an ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policy makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, integrating traditional water management strategies and water reuse technologies. The Deliverable D4.4 (Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis) presents the analysis performed in the Task T4.3 (Robust portfolios planning) for Demo site 1, the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct (AQP) system, Italy. T4.3 makes use of the methodologies developed in the Task T4.1 (Multi-objective water planning portfolios design) and presented in the Deliverable D4.1 (Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions), extending the analysis to future hydro-climatic and socio-economic scenarios.

AQP is one of the largest water distribution systems in Europe and is located in one of the driest areas. The aqueduct network has an extension of 20,000 kilometres, 30 times the length of the Po River, and a transport capacity of over 790 million cubic meters of water every year to ensure drinking water supply to over 4.5 million people. Covering an area of 19,541 km², Apulia is the fifth Italian region in terms of irrigated area and has the highest number of agricultural workers. Agriculture has a central role in the regional economy, and the exposure of community welfare to drought is a major challenge. As shown by our analysis, in recent years, sequential droughts have overstressed the system forcing, in some cases, to water supply curtailments. In this context, the adoption of water reuse technologies can increase water availability and enhance supply reliability, bringing better preparedness for emergencies.

The DAP developed for the AQP system is composed of the following components: i) candidate water portfolios (i.e. combinations of traditional water management options and new water reuse technologies); ii) evaluation indicators to assess - in a multidimensional fashion - the impact of the different portfolios (e.g., cost, water deficit); iii) a mathematical model of the AQP system to simulate the behaviour of the entire water system for the different portfolios under present and future climate and socio-economic scenarios; iv) a multi-objective optimisation engine to select Pareto efficient portfolios; and v) a computationally efficient model reduction of a subpart of the AQP water system (the water distribution network) to make the simulation-based optimisation of water portfolios computationally feasible within the life of the project.

The above components have been originally developed in the Task T4.1 for the baseline scenario (current water demand and hydroclimatic conditions), for which Pareto efficient water portfolios are computed via optimization. Specifically, we considered alternative water portfolios composed of the reservoirs operating policies and the water diversion policy to split the water flows between the aqueduct and irrigation or industrial districts.

The Task T4.3 extends the analysis presented in T4.1 including future hydro-climatic projections, socio-economic drivers, legislative constraint on environmental flows, and technological improvements related to the water loops. Two types of water reuse actions are considered: the first aims at extending the capacity of water treatment and recycling technologies and mainly affects the irrigation and industrial sectors; the second targets the activation of non-conventional water sources such as abandoned wells that would not be usually integrated into the water distribution system.

Our analysis shows that the combined effect of climate and socio-economic changes will dramatically affect the Apulia water system, leading to an unsustainable pressure on the freshwater resources. In addition, the respect of the constraints related to the environmental flows will further reduce the operation space. The adoption of water reuse technologies can remarkably reduce the water deficit, but specific mitigation actions adopted can only partially compensate the effect of climatic and socio-economic changes. In this context, a wide diffusion of the water loops has to be promoted in order to limit a dramatic increase of water shortages and of all the related issues.

To provide a comprehensive overview, we also perform a vulnerability assessment that allows us identifying the extent to which each sector (and each specific site) can be affected by issues related to water scarcity under the different future scenarios considered.

Acronyms and abbreviations

AIP:	Autorità Idrica Pugliese
ANN:	Artificial Neural Network
AQP:	Acquedotto Pugliese
ARPA:	Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione Ambientale (Regional Agency for Environmental Protection)
COM:	Component Object Model
DAF:	Decision Analytics Framework
DAP:	Decision Analytics Platform
DM:	Decision-Maker
DP:	Dynamic Programming
DPS:	Direct Policy Search
ECMWF:	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EFAS:	European Flood Awareness System
EIPLI:	Ente per lo sviluppo dell'Irrigazione e la trasformazione fondiaria in Puglia, Lucania e Irpinia (Organization for the development of irrigation and land transformation in Puglia, Lucania and Irpinia)
EM-DAT:	Emergency Events Database
EMODPS:	Evolutionary Multi-Objective Direct Policy Search
FAO:	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GCM:	Global Circulation Model
GIS:	Geographic Information System
ICT:	Information and Communication Technologies
ID:	Irrigation District
IPCC:	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISPRA:	Istituto superiore per la protezione e la ricerca ambientale (Higher Institute for Environmental Protection and Research)
LSTM:	Long short-term memory
MOEA:	Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm
RBF:	Radial Basis Function
RCM:	Regional Circulation Model
RCP:	Representative Concentration Pathway
RNN:	Recurrent Neural Networks
SDP:	Stochastic Dynamic Programming
SH:	Stakeholder
VBA:	Visual Basic® for Applications
WP:	Work Package

Table of Contents

Deliverable Review and Approval.....	1
Executive summary.....	2
Acronyms and abbreviations.....	3
1 Introduction.....	6
2 The Italian demo site: Apulian Aqueduct.....	7
2.1 System Description.....	7
2.1.1 Apulia Region.....	7
2.1.2 Apulian water system.....	8
3 Decision Analytic Framework.....	11
3.1 Water Portfolios.....	11
3.1.1 Reservoir operations.....	11
3.1.2 Water diverted to the users.....	11
3.1.3 Water loops in the water supply system.....	11
3.1.4 Water loops in the water distribution systems.....	11
3.2 Indicators.....	12
3.3 Scenarios.....	13
3.4 Water portfolios design.....	14
4 Models and tools.....	15
4.1 Strategic model.....	15
4.1.1 Objectives.....	16
4.1.2 Decision variables.....	17
4.2 Surrogate model of Aquator.....	17
4.2.1 Software description.....	17
4.2.2 Original Apulian system implementation.....	20
4.3 Optimisation tool.....	24
4.3.1 Evolutionary multi-objective direct policy search.....	25
4.3.2 Operating policy optimization.....	26
4.5 Baseline scenario.....	28
4.5.1 Hydrological flows.....	28
4.5.2 Water demands.....	29
4.6 Future climate scenarios.....	31
4.6.1 Statistical downscaling.....	33
4.6.2 Inflow projections generation.....	34
4.7 Future drinking demand.....	43
4.8 Water reuse technologies.....	43
4.8.1 Water reclamation.....	43
4.8.2 Reactivation of dismissed wells.....	45
5 Results.....	47
5.1 Experiment design.....	47
5.2 Baseline scenario.....	47
5.3 Environmental flow effect.....	54

5.4	Future climate scenarios	55
5.5	Future drinking demand	57
5.6	Water reuse technology	58
5.7	Vulnerability assessment.....	60
6	Discussion and conclusion	63
	Bibliography.....	64

1 Introduction

This document is the Deliverable D4.4 - *Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis*, part of Work Package 4 activities undertaken in Task T4.3 - *Robust portfolios planning*, aimed at producing of a set of optimally designed water planning portfolios that can robustly deal with the future changes of the hydro-meteorological regimes as well as the socio-economic conditions, exploiting the technological innovation in the field of water reuse.

The goal of WP4 is to design, develop, and test an ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policy-makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, i.e. combinations of traditional water management options and new water reuse technologies, under current and projected water availability and demand conditions. The workflow of WP4 is illustrated in Figure 1: a set of candidate portfolios is first identified in collaboration with local stakeholders, including the local water supply company, water management bodies, and the water authorities. These are evaluated through a simulation-based optimization with respect to a set of indicators (e.g., cost, reliability) under current climate and socio-economic conditions (baseline scenarios) in order to select a subset of portfolios of potential interest for policy-makers (technically Pareto efficient portfolios). The efficient portfolios are further screened in Task T4.3 against a variety of future scenarios to retrieve the most robust ones, i.e., those better performing in the worst conditions. We will refer to the integration of these mathematical modelling components as a Decision Analytic Framework (DAF). The DAF is complemented in T4.2 with visual

Figure 1: The WP4 workflow.

analytics tools to form the ICT-based DAP that will support the in-depth trade-off analysis of water portfolios by policy-makers.

The DAF is composed of a water system model coupled with an optimisation engine. The water system model conceptualises the main natural processes and human decisions at the whole river basin scale and balances accuracy in process characterisation and reduced computational requirements to allow the simulation-based optimisation of the water portfolios. Such optimisation is performed using multi-objective evolutionary algorithms (MOEAs, for a review, see Maier et al., 2014), which generate a set of Pareto-optimal solutions representing the trade-offs across the design indicators. Technically, a portfolio is defined as Pareto-optimal (or nondominated) if no other solution gives a better value for one indicator without degrading the performance in at least one other indicator. The image in the indicator space of the Pareto-optimal solutions is the Pareto front. The advantage of this a-posteriori approach with respect to traditional a-priori methods, such as cost-benefit analysis or multi-attribute value theory, is that decision-makers do not have to state what is preferred in the absence of their understanding of what is attainable (Cohon and Marks, 1975).

In addition, it allows considering heterogeneous and incommensurable utility functions without going through any monetisation process. Finally, MOEAs jointly optimise the planning (i.e. new water loops) and the management (i.e. water infrastructure operations) components of water portfolios.

The report is structured as follows: the next chapter introduces the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct; Chapter 3 describes the main components of the DAF; Chapter 4 presents all the components of the strategic models, the describes the optimization engine, and illustrates the current and future climatic and economic scenarios considered; experimental setting and numerical results are reported in Chapter 5. Chapters 5.7 summarise the main takeaways of the Task T4.3.

It is worth noting that some of the sections of this report, especially in Chapters 2, 3 and 4, fully or partially recall some parts of the Deliverable D4.1 with the aim of providing to the reader the context developed in the previous stages of the project.

2 The Italian demo site: Apulian Aqueduct

2.1 System Description

The Decision Analytics Platform (DAP) is demonstrated on Demo site 1, the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct (AQP), located in the Apulia Region, Italy. In this section, we will illustrate the case study, describe the data used to build the baseline scenario, report an extensive drought analysis, and describe the Aquator model currently used by the AQP water utility (AQP spa) for the operation of the water distribution network.

2.1.1 Apulia Region

The Apulia Region is an area of 19,541 km² located in South Italy and characterised by a Mediterranean climate with hot and dry summers and mild winters. During summer, precipitations are scarce may be missing for months. During winter, rainfalls are limited by the Southern Apennines with respect to the Atlantic depressions; here, rainfalls are shaped by the Mediterranean rising perturbation raids or by the cold air from the north or north-east (Ronco et al., 2017). Apulia is a very vast and differentiated area, mostly articulated in mainland and two peninsulas, the Salento in the south, projecting into the Gulf of Taranto and representing the south-eastern extremity of Italy, and the Gargano Promontory, which is a mountainous part of the region, consisting of the external Apennine thrust belt. The region is characterised by the karstic substrate's high permeability that favours rainwater infiltration. Consequently, there are few surface rivers concentrated in the northern area: Candelaro, Cervaro, Carapelle, Ofanto, while Fortore and Bradano river basins rely on the northern and western boundaries across the Molise and Basilicata regions, respectively (Ronco et al., 2017).

Despite low annual rainfall, scarce endogenous water, and a small hydrographic network, agriculture is a very developed sector in Apulia, mostly based on intensive olive growing, viticulture, and horticulture. As a result, Apulia is the fifth Italian region in terms of irrigated area and volumes of irrigation water used (Sardaro et al., 2018). Apulia has the highest number of agricultural workers among the Italian Regions, and this reveals the tremendous impact that agriculture has, especially on the regional economy and community welfare (Sardaro et al., 2016). More than 80% of the Apulian surface is currently used for agricultural purposes, and about 10% is covered by wild vegetation (Corine Land Cover, 2018¹). The largest part of agricultural land is devoted to arable crops (mainly cereals). Still, the most profitable part is the one related to olives (32%), vineyards (9%), citrus (3%), and vegetables (2%) productions (Ronco et al., 2017). These considerations make the economic dependence of this Region on agricultural yield even more evident. Given the scarcity of surface water, Apulian aquifers were a valuable water source in terms of quality and quantity in the past, hence extremely important to agriculture. These resources have been increasingly exploited since the early decades of the last century. To date, despite scientific, technical, and cultural progress, management and governance policies couldn't avoid the gradual depletion of these limited resources (Polemio et al., 2009).

The Apulian territory is divided into Irrigation Districts (Consorzi di Bonifica) storing, supplying, and distributing water to farmers through irrigation networks and covering 90% (Lamaddalena et al., 2004) of the Region surface, as shown in Figure 2. An Irrigation District is an Italian public legal authority that takes care of the operation and maintenance of public reclamation works. In addition, it monitors privates' activities in the area of competence, manages hydraulic security, and operates reservoirs and irrigation water systems.

Apulia counts six Irrigation Districts that are different for dimensions, climate, and crops. Hereafter they are presented with their extension:

- Consorzio di Bonifica di Arneo - 252,981 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Capitanata - 441,545 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Gargano - 150,337 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Stornara e Tara - 142,949 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Terre d'Apulia - 569,807ha

¹ <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

- Consorzio di Bonifica di Ugento Li Foggi - 189,494 ha.

Figure 2: Apulian Region Irrigation Districts.

2.1.2 Apulian water system

To provide water to the seven Irrigation Districts and other water users all over the Region, a vast and complex network of pipes and canals has been built. The adduction system has been developing for one century by successive additions to the main canal, named “Canale Principale”, crossing from North to South the whole region and conveying spring water to towns and cities. The hydro-morphological features of the Apulia Region, which impede the stock of large volume of surface waters, required the development of large interregional water transfer schemes, collecting water flowing from surrounding Regions (Basilicata, Campania, Calabria, and Molise), to meet the Apulian water demand (Ronco et al., 2017). Overall, the system now features five major reservoirs: Occhito (on the Fortore river), Locone (on the homonymous creek), Conza (on the Ofanto river), Monte Cotugno (on the Sinni River), and Pertusillo (on the Agri River), as well as the Sele-Calore springs (Caposele), and several wells. It is important to notice that this territory is part of Appennino Meridionale Water Authority, which has an overall sufficient water availability but is not evenly distributed. There is thus the need of transferring the resource from confining regions and for long distances.

The main adduction and distribution scheme in the Apulia Region, is managed by Acquedotto Pugliese S.p.A. (AQP spa²). AQP is one of the largest and oldest European water utilities, operating in this area for over a century. To provide drinking and irrigation water to the entire Region, one of the world's most extended adduction systems (around 5000 km) has been built. The main supply network is structured in six water conveyance schemes: Sele-Calore, Pertusillo, Sinni, Fortore, Locone, Ofanto, distributed across four regions and all interconnected to transfer water from one scheme to the other (see Figure 3).

² <https://www.aqp.it/>

Figure 3: AQP network with main canals and water sources (reservoirs and natural spring - triangles).

Nowadays, AQP spa manages a water network of 21,000 km (30 times the length of the Po River), including the urban distribution networks, about 11,000 km of sewerage networks, and 184 treatment plants. More than half of the network was built before 1970 and requires continuous maintenance and modernisation (Balacco et al., 2017). When failures in water supply occur during the irrigation phase, crops are exposed to risk, and farmers resort to private wells to guarantee the amount of water needed.

Table 1 reports data from “Autorità di Bacino Regione Puglia, Relazione Finale Vol. 1 – Il Comparto Agricolo Pugliese (ABRP1)” representing the average volumes of water distributed from each Consortium with the associated source of supply.

Table 1: Average Water Distribution

Irrigation District	Source of supply	Supplied water [Cubic meters/year]	Total Supplied water [Cubic meters/year]
Arneo	Wells	498373	498373
Capitanata	Occhito Reservoir	63058333	100264712
	Ofanto River	10914123	
	Marana Capacciotti	26292256	
Gargano	Springs	178099	185566
	Wells	8467	
Stornara e Tara	Monte Cotugno Reservoir	23098127	39755333
	San Giuliano Reservoir	16657206	
Terre d'Apulia	Locone Reservoir	3842750	12390775
	Ofanto River	7875571	
	Wells	672454	
Ugento Li Foggi	Wells	1289079	1289079

The AQP network scheme reported in Figure 3 represents the basis for the strategic model of the system that is necessary to perform the numerical experiments. The topology of the model is illustrated in Figure 4, and its components are:

- Water reservoirs
- Water sources that can be distinguished in hydrological basins drained by the reservoirs, natural springs and wells
- Diversion mechanisms that distribute the water flow to the different users
- Agricultural districts
- Industrial districts
- Drinking water network

Figure 4: Topologic scheme of the strategic simulation model of the Apulia water system.

As shown in Figure 4, the system can be split into two subsystems. The first is the water storage system, managed by the districts (Consorti in the Italian terminology) that operate the reservoirs and supply water to the agricultural and industrial users. The second is the water distribution system, managed by AQP spa, that has to provide the potable water flows to the municipalities.

3 Decision Analytic Framework

3.1 Water Portfolios

The twofold goals of WP4 are to understand the trade-offs of the system and discover planning and management strategies that will withstand plausible, challenging conditions in the region (e.g., prolonged droughts, increasing demand, and contingencies in the system). Both goals require extensive exploration to understand the impacts of different hydroclimatic and socio-economic scenarios on the system's ability to meet its multi-sectorial demands. We build the relationship between the system's inputs and the relevant performance indicators described in the following. The idea is that the response model preserves the input and output behaviour of the original simulation-based model while removing the need to run a process-based model that will allow us to understand which candidate alternatives yield the best benefit for the system. For the Apulian system, several candidate water portfolios were identified, these are related to the management of existing infrastructure, such as reservoir control, increasing infrastructure capacity, such as doubling pipeline capacity and their connections within the system, re-activating non-conventional sources such as wells that are not currently considered into the system, as well as the integration of reuse technologies in feasible small water loops.

This deliverable extends the baseline exploring a number of water portfolios that consider future projections of the climate and of the future drinking demand pattern. The core of the analysis is represented by the assessment of the impacts generated by the implementation of water reuse technologies.

3.1.1 Reservoir operations

Coordinated reservoir operations can play a key role in the system's reliability. For our initial abstraction of the Apulian Aqueduct system, we focus on five reservoirs that are relevant for the analysis of our performance indicators since they directly feed the system, and along with other sources such as Calore and Sele, along with other lateral flows not quantified in our analysis, contribute to the available water in the system. These reservoirs are mainly parallel to each other, that is, there is no cascading effect, hence the mass-balance dynamics can be computed separately.

3.1.2 Water diverted to the users

Concerning the diversions to final users, we consider two different cases depending on the sector. Irrigation and industrial water demands are associated to each reservoir. In the model, the water is thus directly diverted to each irrigation or industrial district and used to compute the corresponding water deficit. Conversely, it is not possible to assign a given drinking water demand to each reservoir due to the presence of the aqueduct, a large infrastructure that can transfer remarkable amount of water flows tens of kilometres away from the source (e.g., reservoir, natural springs, wells). A model of the drinking water distribution networks is thus implemented to accurately reproduce the dynamic of the physical system.

3.1.3 Water loops in the water supply system

The percent of water reuse refers to the volume of water that can be extended through water reuse technologies for the identified water loops. This alternative depends upon several specifications about the foreseen technology such as its scalability, that is, the volume that can be treated and integrated into the system, the costs for installation, operation, and maintenance, as well as the time when the technology can be scaled and incorporated into the system. The implementation of some candidate alternatives in the strategic system will enable us to understand and quantify the impact of water reuse technologies. The water loops in the supply system will allow industrial and irrigation districts to partially satisfy the demands, thus reducing the pressure on the freshwater resources.

3.1.4 Water loops in the water distribution systems

These alternatives will also be supplemented with a few structural decisions regarding the drinking water distribution system, which are currently under consideration by the AQP spa. For instance, integrating alternative water sources, such as impounded sources which are not currently part of the network that could be reactivated

and could increase the reliability of the system. This includes the reactivation of several wells, which provide a good opportunity to explore treatment technologies.

3.2 Indicators

ProjectÔ follows the Participatory and Integrated Planning procedure by Soncini-Sessa et al. (2007) to infer and represent decision-makers (DM) and stakeholders (SH) preferences. First, stakeholders with similar issues and priorities are grouped into sectors (e.g., irrigation supply, drinking water). Then, for each sector, an evaluation criterion is specified and associated with an index that DMs and/or SHs can use for the comparative assessment of the portfolios with respect to the criterion. The index can be defined either on an ordinal scale (qualitative) or on a cardinal scale (quantitative). It must be a function of the portfolio that describes the preferred direction of change embedded in the evaluation criterion.

The index supports the pairwise comparison of alternative water portfolios. For example, given two portfolios P1 and P2, a DM should be able to select the “preferred portfolio” with respect to a given criterion by contrasting the values that the index assumes under P1 and P2. The repetition of such pairwise comparison across a set of portfolios allows the definition of the complete ranking of the portfolios with respect to the criterion expressed by the index. In principle, the index value can be directly estimated by interviewing the SHs or a representative expert when this is not feasible (Figure 5a). Yet, this direct approach frequently leads to subjective and hardly acceptable evaluations, and its implementation might become extremely difficult when the planning process involves many alternative portfolios. Therefore, an automated procedure is more appropriate to reproduce the SHs/Expert evaluations to compute the index (Figure 5b). The strong participation of both DMs and SHs is crucial in this step to ensure the results of the decision-making process will be perceived as trustable: direct involvement of the decision-maker herself in the modelling process is the unique way to make credible models: these can be built only by people who are familiar with both the problem and the institutional setting in which the problem is to be addressed (Loucks et al., 1985).

In ProjectÔ, each index value can be computed as a function of the simulated trajectories of the relevant model variables (Figure 5c), such as water level in a specific river section, water flow in an irrigation canal, water flow through turbines in a hydropower plant. Such computation of the index is generally performed in two steps (Figure 5d). First, an evaluation indicator measures the effects of a portfolio in physical units. Then the value of this indicator is mapped into the actual satisfaction of the DMs’ or SH’ criterion by means of a value function.

It is worth noticing that the value of an indicator expressed in physical units could differ from the level of satisfaction of the associated criterion returned by the value function. For example, if the indicator quantifies the water level excess above a critical flood threshold and portfolios P1, P2, and P3 produce different values of this indicator all above the threshold, the corresponding level of satisfaction can be null for all the three portfolios.

In some cases, it might be difficult to formulate an indicator directly associated with the index used by DMs or SHs for the evaluation of their criteria. For example, an indicator related to flood protection could be flood damage, which requires formalising a relationship between the water level in a flood event and the economic damages produced by the flood. However, defining such a relationship is very site-specific and generally requires ad-hoc data collections that may prevent its use in practice. In these cases, the original flood damage indicator might be replaced by a proxy indicator measuring the flooded area rather than the economic damage (Figure 5e). The proxy indicator is a variable in a logical relationship with the evaluation criterion associated with the index and related to the effects

Figure 5: Alternative approaches for the definition of evaluation index (adapted from Soncini-Sessa et al., 2007a).

of the portfolios through a functional, objective, and potentially quantifiable link (Keeney and Raiffa, 1976). Then, DM/SHs can define a value function for the proxy indicator to map this latter into a level of satisfaction. The proxy indicator hence assumes the role of an indirect ordinal estimator of the evaluation criterion, and the degree of satisfaction of such criterion can be quantified through the value assumed by the proxy indicator, ultimately replacing the need for computing the original indicator.

In the Apulian site, the assessment indicators identified will aid the evaluation of planning and management policies for water distribution networks when incorporating alternative sources and water-reuse technologies within the system. We identify sustainable and efficient water management goals that respond to regional water needs while minimising the total costs of the distribution network and the technology costs. All the objectives will be optimised at a daily time scale for a planning horizon of $365T$, where T is the number of years considered in the planning time frame.

The main criteria can be categorised as follows:

1. Minimise water reuse costs. This objective is divided into two measurements, first, a water reduction cost related to the adoption of technologies for water reuse which is dependent upon the volume of water that will be treated by the reuse technology and is proportional to the percent water reduction in the system and the cost of the treatment technology at each point in time. The second evaluates the costs reduced by substituting pumping for irrigation where small water loops are implemented in the vicinity of the irrigation district.
2. Minimise costs in the water distribution network. The Apulian Aqueduct Authority currently optimises the distribution cost, and we also account for our objective formulation. The total cost of the water distribution network can be described as the sum of the operational costs, pumping costs, treatment costs, and rehabilitation or maintenance costs. Distribution points differentiate these costs.
3. Minimise water supply deficits. These objectives are considered for the following water demand sectors: 1) drinking supply; 2) farmers; 3) industry. A priority for suitable management policies is to provide a reliable source of drinking water to nearly 4.5 million users that depend upon the Apulian Aqueduct; other competing demands in the region are for farmers and for industrial use. This indicator aims to minimise the water supply deficit for each one of these users by minimising the squared difference between demand and the actual releases in cubic meters, where larger deficits are penalised more than smaller deficits.

Due to the narrow knowledge of some parts of the system and the limited availability of the dataset provided by other partners of the project, not all the indicators presented above can be computed in a reasonable way in each position of the system. We thus limit our optimisation procedure to a subset of indicators that, however, guarantees to be compliant with the scope of Project O.

3.3 Scenarios

The simulation of the system requires the definition of a scenario, i.e., a set of input variables that we cannot control in the context of our optimal management problem but influence the dynamics of the system. Typical examples of these variables are the inflows, the water demands and the treatment costs.

In this project, the scenario is defined as the set $\omega = \{q_1^h; wirr_0^{h-1}; wind_0^{h-1}; wdri_0^{h-1}; cdri_0^{h-1}\}$, where q_1^h is the vector of all inflows, $wirr_0^{h-1}$, $wind_0^{h-1}$, $wdri_0^{h-1}$ are the specific water demands for irrigation, industrial and drinking use respectively; and $cdri_0^{h-1}$ represents the vector of all adduction, treatment, and distribution costs depending on the structural configuration and used technologies.

In the Deliverable D4.1, we focus on the baseline scenario ($\bar{\omega}$), constituted by observed historical inflows and structural factors.

Our framework is not limited to historical conditions but allows us to consider the management optimisation over a future scenario ($\hat{\omega}$), which will be the object of the Deliverable D4.4. The future scenarios analysis allows us to consider potential changes in the hydrologic, structural, and economic conditions. These changes in the external drivers will lead to new management strategies specifically designed to be efficient for the future system's conditions.

3.4 Water portfolios design

As said, the DAF requires defining the water system operation as an optimisation problem to derive an efficient management strategy. To this aim, the indicators (all of them or just a subset) presented in the previous section can be used as the objectives to be minimised (if costs) or maximised (if benefits). Following a multi-objective approach, we can consider a generic K -dimensional vector of operating objectives $J = [J^1, \dots, J^K]$ for the DAF optimisation.

Each single objective function is formulated as follows:

$$J_{\omega}^k = \Psi_{q_1, \dots, q_h} \left[\Phi_{0, \dots, h} \left(g_1^k(s_0, u_0, q_1), \dots, g_h^k(s_h) \right) \right] \quad k = 1, \dots, K \quad (1)$$

where

- s_t is the state of the system at time t ,
- u_t is the control decision taken to manage the system operation,
- q_{t+1} is the stochastic disturbance,
- ω is the scenario,
- h is the length of the time horizon,
- $g_t^k(\cdot)$ is the step cost (or benefit) relative to the k^{th} objective,
- $\Psi[\cdot]$ is a disturbance filtering criterion (e.g., expected value) for filtering the uncertainty introduced by the disturbance q_{t+1} ,
- $\Phi(\cdot)$ is an operator for time aggregation (e.g., mean or sum).

The core of the optimal control problem is the management policy that defines the control action as a function of the information available at time t , I_t :

$$u_t = p(I_t) \quad (2)$$

Most of the times, I_t corresponds to the state of the system s_t . However, it is possible to include in the information vector every variable known at time t , including forecasted values for the future steps or exogenous information that can be useful to estimate the future evolution of the system (see, for instance, the drought indexes discussed in D4.1). Given the objectives vector and the operating policy, the optimisation problem is simply defined as $\underset{p}{\text{opt}} J$.

The model's equations representing the optimisation problem constraints, the characterisation of the objectives and the algorithm adopted to solve the problem are described in the following chapters.

4 Models and tools

In this chapter, we provide an in-depth description of the strategic model presented in Figure 4, which is reported for convenience in Figure 6a. We then present the model's components and describe the elements and tools necessary for the system's simulation and optimisation.

4.1 Strategic model

The key components of the strategic simulation model adopted in this work are the five water reservoirs Occhito, Conza, Locone, Pertusillo and Monte Cotugno, each draining its catchment. Catchments are not modelled as we adopt a partial-data driven approach, which directly relies on observational data for the uncontrolled and control-independent components of the system. Streamflow data are derived as net inflow by inverting equation 3 and using historical time series of storages and releases. Two other water sources are implemented in the strategic model: the natural springs of Cassano and Caposele and the Salento region wells system that extracts groundwater flows from the aquifer.

Downstream of each reservoir, a diversion dam distributes the release among different water users. With the only exception of Monte Cotugno reservoir, which is used to supply water to an industrial district, all the dams serve both an irrigation district and the drinking water distribution network.

We illustrate the mathematical model of the AQP topology considering a generic single-reservoir model connected through a river stretch with a diversion point (Figure 6b) serving three different types of users (agricultural, industrial, and potable water). The environmentally vulnerable river stretches downstream of the reservoir are usually protected by the legislation by means of a constraint on the water release (the minimum environmental flow). Note that, each reservoir usually is also connected to a hydropower plant. However, since this aspect is not considered in this study, we did not report this element in the figure.

Figure 6: Topological scheme of the strategic simulation model (a) and illustrative example of a single-reservoir subsystem (b).

The reservoir dynamics are described by the water volume's mass balance equation s_t stored in the reservoir at the beginning of month t :

$$s_{t+1} = s_t + q_{t+1} - r_{t+1} \quad (3)$$

where q_{t+1} is the net inflow to the reservoir (i.e., inflow minus evaporation losses and other minor phenomena such as the seepage losses) in the time interval $[t; t + 1)$ and r_{t+1} the volume of water released in the same time interval. In the adopted notation, the time subscript of a variable indicates the instant when its value is

deterministically known. The storage s_t is observed at time t , whereas the inflow has subscript $t + 1$, denoting the realisation of the inflow stochastic process in the time interval $[t; t + 1)$.

The release is defined as $r_{t+1} = f(s_t, u_t, q_{t+1})$, where $f(\cdot)$ describes the non-linear, stochastic relation between the release decision determined by the operating policy, i.e., $u_t = p(\cdot)$, and the actual release r_{t+1} (Piccardi and Soncini-Sessa, 1991). The actual release at the end of the time interval is generally equal to the release decision unless physical constraints prohibit it (e.g., if the prescribed release lies outside the minimum and maximum allowable releases, if there is insufficient water to meet the prescribed release, or if the prescribed release would result in the reservoir storage capacity being exceeded).

The water released from the reservoir is distributed to the different users through a regulated diversion mechanism. The volume of water diverted to agricultural districts, industries and the aqueduct are $rirr_{t+1}$, $rind_{t+1}$ and $rdri_{t+1}$ and should ideally fulfil the corresponding water demands. Downstream the irrigation diversion, the water volume that is left in the river should guarantee adequate environmental conditions to preserve the ecosystem.

As said, the generic elements described above must be individually calibrated and validated and then integrated to build the model of the entire Apulia water system (see Figure 6a). For instance, each reservoir has its own characteristics (e.g. level-surface-storage relationship and specific functions that define its minimum and maximum releases) that have to be incorporated in the corresponding model component.

It is worth noting that the AQP component in Figure 6a represents the water distribution system implemented with the Aquator tool and used to compute the AQP-related indicators (drinking water distribution deficit and cost). This is the only component of the strategic model that is not directly implemented in C++ but requires executing external software. Evaluating the water portfolios and identifying the Pareto efficient ones requires exploring millions (or thousands) of candidate solutions via simulation. Given its real-to-run ratio (a simulation on a one-year time horizon requires approximatively one hour of computing time), Aquator is not a suitable tool for our scope. To avoid these practical and computational issues, we use a surrogate model that will be presented in detail in Section 4.2.

4.1.1 Objectives

When considering complex water systems such as the Apulia one, several stakeholders with conflicting interests are usually affected by the reservoir's operations and the diversion. These conflicting interests are captured by the indicators introduced in Section 3.2, which are here converted into the objectives of the optimisation framework. Within the strategic model represented in Figure 6a, three main stakeholders' sectors (i.e., agriculture, industry, and potable water distribution) may be affected by the system's operations. Their conflicting interests can be thus modelled as a four-objectives vector $\mathbf{J} = [J^{irr}, J^{ind}, J^{dri,d}, J^{dri,c}]$, whose components are the following:

- Squared irrigation deficit:

$$J^{irr} = \frac{1}{h} [\sum_{t=0}^{h-1} (\max(wirr_t - rirr_{t+1}, 0))^2] \quad (4)$$

where $wirr_t$ and $rirr_{t+1}$ are the irrigation water demand and supply.

- Squared industrial deficit:

$$J^{ind} = \frac{1}{h} [\sum_{t=0}^{h-1} (\max(wind_t - rind_{t+1}, 0))^2] \quad (5)$$

where $wind_t$ and $rind_{t+1}$ are the industrial water demand and supply respectively.

- Potable water deficit, $J^{dri,d}$:

unlike the two objectives defined above, we cannot directly compute $J^{dri,d}$ as the deficit between the drinking water demand, $wdri_t$, and the corresponding supply, $rdri_{t+1}$. The reason is that there is not a direct correspondence between demand and supply: the water flows are released in the complex water distribution system implemented in Aquator.

- Drinking water distribution cost, $J^{dri,c}$:

As $J^{dri,d}$, also the distribution cost cannot be easily expressed with single mathematical formulation but requires a specific model (again, Aquator).

Note that the objectives are computed in different points of the system, i.e., in each agricultural and industrial district and in the specific points defined in Aquator. However, this would generate an unsustainable number of

objectives. We thus decide to aggregate the objectives by summing the values obtained in the different points of the system. Intermediate solutions with partial aggregation of the objectives can be easily considered with our software. The four objectives considered are deficits or costs and thus are to be minimised.

4.1.2 Decision variables

The optimisation of the system management requires to operate the reservoir dams and the diversions. The reservoir dam operation problem requires sequential release decisions u_t to be taken at discrete time instants based on the current state of the system (t, s_t) (i.e., time, reservoir storage) or the pair time, current information (t, I_t) . The decision u_t is determined at each time step by a closed-loop operating policy $u_t = p(t, s_t)$. In order to solve the system management optimisation problem, this operating policy $p(\cdot)$ must be thus optimised with respect to multiple objectives. Note that, in our formulation of the problem, u_t also contains the fraction of water to be distributed between the different water users in the diversion nodes and the total amount of water captured by the well fields. This multi-objective optimisation problem must be solved for each possible portfolio, namely every combination of possible infrastructural interventions (i.e., different distribution network and irrigation expansion). For each portfolio, a set of Pareto-optimal solutions (i.e., operating policies) will be thus generated according to the trade-off among conflicting objectives (see previous section).

4.2 Surrogate model of Aquator

Under the supervision of the University of Palermo, AQP spa built a complete model of its distribution network a few years ago, using a well-known commercial software, Aquator. In this section, we give an overview of the software, describe the implementation of the complete model for the Apulian case study, and report the identification of the surrogate model.

4.2.1 Software description

Aquator is a software application produced by Oxford Scientific to simulate complex water resource systems with a daily time-step. The real system is represented by a schematic graph model built using a 'drag & drop' user interface, selecting appropriate components from the Aquator Toolbox.

Examples of components are river and groundwater abstractions, uni- and bi-directional links (to connect other components), blenders (to mix incoming water in a specified ratio or to maintain a specified level of water quality), bulk supplies (for example, to force usage of the entire maximum amount that is available), catchments (to define a simple flow series of daily or monthly average values), demand centres, discharges, diversions, gauging stations, hydro-generators, pumping stations, regulators and reservoirs, terminations, water treatment plants. Components could be eventually grouped to encapsulate uniform rules for the contained elements. Each component or group could be associated with a license to limit the amount of water supplied over a defined period.

Figure 7: An example of a simple model defined in Aquator (from the Aquator Manual).

An example of a simple model considering different types of components and links is reported in Figure 7.

Once the components have been linked together and all specific hydrological parameters assigned, the model may be run over any pre-defined horizon. At the end of the simulation, it is possible (see Figure 8) to produce a complete

report of the behaviour of all the components and the selected variables may be displayed in graphical and tabular form.

The main features of Aquator are the following:

- Component-based. Models are constructed by joining together components representing hydrological entities, using an intuitive point-and-click user interface. These components encapsulate the operating rules that govern their use. For example, a reservoir component will typically have control curves that the reservoir operating rules will use to determine releases from the reservoir.
- Customisable and extensible. It incorporates Microsoft® Visual Basic® for Applications (VBA), the same technology used in the Microsoft Office suite of applications. With this tool, the user can optionally customise the operating rules of any component. In the same way, third-party developers could add additional components.
- Standards and Open architecture based. The design and implementation of Aquator components and Aquator itself are based on an industry-standard open architecture called COM (Component Object Model) defined by Microsoft and used as the VBA architecture.
- Cooperative. The Aquator application itself can be used as a type of component. For example, a GIS (Geographic Information System) application could automatically load Aquator and create a model from the information held in the GIS database.
- Globally optimized. The facility “Aqua Solver” looks for the ‘best’ solution for water allocation to meet demand.

Each model and parameters configuration are organised as a different project, stored in a single database. The current version of Aquator uses an SQLite database file (AXVDBS extension). An Aquator database can contain any number of projects (models), time series and profile data, and results from model runs.

Input time-series, as, for example, the water demand of each demand centre, could be imported in Aquator, with the “copy & paste” feature from clipboard data or with the excel import wizard. Simulation results could be exported as plain text files (in “csv” format) or in excel format.

During each simulation day, water is moved according to the input data, the rules associated with each component, and the connectivity (the network) defined in the model.

Figure 8: The Aquator's form to visualize simulation results summary.

There are five phases to such water movements:

1. Any catchments in the model add to river flows at the start of the day. Such flows may be controlled by a simple time series of values or possibly by a full catchment model running at the same time.
2. The system's river regulators may augment river flows to satisfy river flow constraints and today's expected abstractions. If the forecasting option is turned on, then releases may also be made to satisfy flow constraints and predicted abstractions on future days.
3. Demand centres then try to satisfy their demands by drawing water from any or all available supplies, such as river abstractions, groundwater abstractions, reservoirs, etc. Demand is typically specified by a profile of daily demand values repeated each year but can be defined in other ways.
4. Reservoirs refill as necessary from their available supplies according to built-in rules governing refilling.
5. At the end of the day, any reservoir which has had excess water pushed into it will spill into its attached river spillway, possibly leading to further spills from any other downstream connected reservoirs.

These movements of water could be limited considering different physical and legal constraints, eventually specifying the order in which operators, if any, release water. Also, the order in which the demand calculations are advanced could be defined automatically or manually, assuming different importance for different demand centres. Each day all the calculations following a defined advance order of components are completed before the calculations for the next advance order are started.

The optimisation algorithm could minimise both water deficits and costs, eventually considering together in a weighted combination.

4.2.2 Original Apulian system implementation

AQP spa operates all the services of storage, adduction, purification, and distribution of water for civil use, sewerage, and wastewater purification, including refinement for agricultural reuse.

The water supply system managed by AQP spa consists of several interconnected aqueduct networks with a transport potential of over 790 million cubic meters of water every year. Every day AQP spa enters its own aqueduct system on average 1.5 Mm³. It ensures the drinking water supply of over 4.5 million inhabitants distributed in Puglia, Basilicata, and Campania.

The water sources consist of natural springs for 29%, from artificial reservoirs for over 50%, and finally from over 200 wells. All fall within the Southern Apennine District and, overall, constitute a sufficient but not homogeneously distributed water availability and therefore require significant transfers between different Regions: from Molise to Campania and Puglia, from Lazio to Campania, from Campania to Puglia and Basilicata, and from Basilicata to Puglia and Calabria. The construction of the model required the definition of the monthly requests from the demand centres, assumed equal to the values delivered by AQP spa in 2012. An annual series of average monthly inflows was adopted for each reservoir, calculated based on historical values. Over 500 arches were modelled to connect over 250 nodes, including 4 hydroelectric plants, 6 lifting plants and 6 purification plants, 5 large reservoirs, 2 natural springs and over 30 groups of wells. A partial representation of the whole model is in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Sketch of a portion of the drinking water distribution scheme implemented in Aquator to give an idea of the complexity of the network.

The software carries out a global daily optimisation of the allocation of resources in terms of minimum cost and maximum satisfaction of requests, considering at the same time the losses in the sections of the channel and the plants as well as the maximum flow capacities.

The model represents the current hydraulic scheme and the existent pumping and hydropower systems and purification plants of the available sources. It also allows you to simulate hypothetical water scarcity scenarios and possible structural interventions. For example, the simulation of a sudden rupture of the aqueduct fed by the Monte Cotugno reservoir (one of the main water carriers of the system) was achieved, with the consequent zeroing of the water supply that it normally guarantees.

The drinking water distribution implemented in the Aquator could be nested in the strategic model to compute the drinking water deficit and the AQP distribution costs, the two objectives that represent the performance of the aqueduct management. However, this would lead to huge computational costs (a computing time greater than 4000 days for a 10-year horizon and 10,000 function evaluation, a relatively small number for a many-objective problem as the one at hand), making the problem practically intractable due to the high number of simulations required to find reasonable results in the optimisation procedure.

Figure 10: Surrogate modelling framework.

A widely adopted method to solve this issue consists in building a surrogate model (sometimes named also response surface) to replace the original one (Aquator in this case) (Castelletti et al., 2010a; Castelletti et al., 2010b; Castelletti et al., 2011). The surrogate model is not required to describe the physical processes with the same level of detail of the original high-fidelity model it surrogates; its aim is to reproduce the relationship between a set of input variables (i.e., the water flows released into the aqueduct into the aqueduct) and a corresponding set of outputs (drinking water deficit and the distribution costs) in a straightforward and computationally efficient way. A schematic representation of the surrogate modelling framework is reported in Figure 10.

The implementation of a surrogate model usually follows a 3-step procedure:

1. Input/output samples generation via design of experiments (sampling of the input space) and simulation of the original high-fidelity model.
2. Selection of the surrogate structure and optimisation of its parameters.
3. Testing phase and evaluation of the accuracy of the surrogate.

In the first phase, we generate the input/output pairs (see Figure 10) running multiple parallel simulation of Aquator. These data constitute the dataset used in the surrogate model identification process. We sample the input space following two different kinds of experiments. The first consists of a grid search approach with an exhaustive evaluation of the rectangular grid. The specific values for each input are selected basing on a statistical analysis of the range of values covered by the historical data. Minimum and maximum water flows into the aqueduct are selected as extreme values. In addition, we consider two intermediate values (selected looking at the density functions of the data). Using this rectangular grid (all the possible combinations are considered), we are sure to cover the whole input hyperspace and to avoid using the surrogate model in extrapolation.

The second set of experiments makes use of the time series available. By means of a clustering procedure (performed by the mean-shift algorithm), we identify the pattern in the historical data and make use of the centroids that are representative of the process. Historical data are fundamental to improve the accuracy of the surrogate model in the areas of the hypervolume containing the combinations of inputs that are more likely to occur in the future, since they occurred in the past.

The second step requires to select a suitable architecture for the reduced model and to train it. Machine learning models are usually adopted to this aim for their flexibility and high performance in terms of accuracy and computing time. Here we adopt artificial neural networks with a feed-forward structure. As reported in Figure 11, the model receives as input the water flow discharged into the aqueduct (from the reservoirs, the natural springs and the wells) and the water demand pattern and computes the two AQP objectives: drinking water deficit and the associated distribution costs.

Figure 11: Neural architecture of the Aquator surrogate model.

The neural network is implemented in Python³ programming language using Keras⁴, a high-level open-source library that provides an interface for TensorFlow⁵. Keras provides built-in functions for building neural architectures and auto-differentiation algorithms for their training. Our implementation allows to consider an arbitrary number of hidden neurons and layers, and different activation functions. In addition, we compare a wide range of gradient-based algorithms for the model’s training. According to the traditional guidelines in the field, input and output variables are rescaled into the range [0; 1] to avoid numerical issues.

In term of coding, the main issue is that we identified the surrogate model in Python, while the main routine for simulation and optimisation is in C++. In principle, it is possible to call the Python model inside the C++ routine (for instance, making use of a wrapper), but this would unavoidably slow down the execution of the code. We thus decided to store the optimal parameters’ values computed in Python in text files and load them into C++. The neural architecture is thus rebuilt in native C++ to delete any possible source of inefficiency in the program execution.

As it is common practice in the machine learning applications, we split the available dataset generated by Aquator simulation, into: train, validation and test subset. As suggested by its name, the first is used to compute the gradients of the model’s parameters (i.e., weights and biases) during the optimisation. The second is not directly involved in the gradient descend, but it is hold out to monitor the risk of overfitting and to set the value of the hyperparameters.

Figure 12: Loss function evolution during the training epochs (first 40 epochs shown for an 6-neuron architecture)

³ <https://www.python.org/>

⁴ <https://keras.io/>

⁵ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

Figure 12 shows an example of the MSE evolution during the epochs of optimisation. The training loss function rapidly decreases in the first epochs and then keep evolving with a marginal improvement to a final value. MSE trends in training and validation are almost coincident, meaning that the model is not overfitting the training data.

We performed a grid search on the following hyperparameters:

- training algorithm (stochastic gradient descent and Adam optimiser);
- non-linear activation function (linear, sigmoid, rectified linear unit);
- batch size;
- learning rate;
- number of neurons in the hidden layer.

This latter is a crucial hyperparameter since it defines the surrogate model’s architecture. As shown in Figure 13, we obtain high accuracy with a limited number of neurons. With 8 neurons, the R^2 is higher than 0.99, and this value does not improve significantly when adding more hidden units, meaning that it can be considered as an

Figure 13: Surrogate model performance obtained with a different complexity (in terms of number of neurons in the hidden layer).

appropriate model complexity. Given the high performance obtained with a single-layer neural network, we do not test deep architectures (with more than one hidden layer). This relatively simple architecture allows limiting the computational cost, whose increment would turn out to be critical in the policy identification stage.

Once the neural surrogate model has been identified, the usual testing phase is performed to assess the model accuracy and to check the model’s appropriateness for our task (e.g., absence of under/overfitting on the training or validation datasets). Each panel of Figure 14 reports the output obtained simulating Aquator and the corresponding value (i.e., computed with the same inputs) estimated by the surrogate model.

Perfect estimations lie on the diagonal line (in blue in the figure), that is the set of all points for which the Aquator output is equal to the surrogate estimation. As it can be seen, in all the considered cases, the points are well aligned on the perfect-estimation line. This means that our surrogate model provides solutions with high accuracy and the absence of overfitting.

The numerical values of the R^2 scores of the surrogate model obtained on the train, validation and test set are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Surrogate model accuracy in terms of R^2 , computed on train, validation and test set (8 hidden neurons).

Output variable	Train	Validation	Test
Drinking water deficit	0.998	0.998	0.998
AQP distribution cost	0.997	0.997	0.997

The performance index reported in the table further confirms that the surrogate model is not overfitting the values obtained by the Aquator simulation. Conversely, the surrogate has high precision and generalisation capability. It can thus substitute the original aqueduct simulation model in the C++ routine.

Figure 14: Comparison between Aquator output and corresponding surrogate values for training, validation and test set. The blue line represents the perfect estimation, i.e., corresponding Aquator and surrogate values.

4.3 Optimisation tool

The design problem of an optimal operating policy for water systems traditionally employs dynamic programming (DP) and its stochastic extension (SDP) (Yeh, 1985). SDP formulates the operating policy design problem as a sequential decision-making process, where a decision taken now produces an immediate reward, affects the next system state and, through that, all the subsequent rewards. The search for optimal policies employs value functions defined over a discrete (or discretised) state-decision space, which are obtained by looking ahead to future events and computing a backed-up value.

The decision u_t is determined at each time step by an operating policy:

$$u_t = p(t, s_t) \quad (6)$$

and the state of the system is the reservoir storage s_t , which is altered according to the transition function described in equation 3). The sequence of states over the time horizon defines a system trajectory, which allows the evaluation of the performance of the operating policy p by means of the objective function defined in section 4.1.1. The optimal policy p^* is hence obtained by solving the following problem:

$$p^* = \arg \min_p J \quad (7)$$

The DP-family methods solve this optimisation problem by estimating the expected long-term cost of a policy for each state s_t , at time t by means of the value function, defined over a discrete grid of states and decisions:

$$H_t(s_t) = \min_{u_t} \Psi_{q_{t+1}} [\Phi_t(g_t(s_t, u_t, q_{t+1}), H_{t+1}(s_{t+1}))] \quad (8)$$

where $g_t(\cdot)$ is the time separable immediate cost function associated to the transition from state s_t to state s_{t+1} under the decision u_t . The modelling assumptions required by SDP for its application are finite domains of state, decision, and disturbance variables, time-separability of objective functions and constraints. These relatively mild assumptions imply, in theory, wide applicability of SDP to many problems, but in practice, its adoption is challenged by three curses (dimensionality, modelling, and multiple objectives) that considerably limit its use in complex real-life problems (Giuliani et al., 2016).

The computational cost of SDP grows exponentially with the state vector dimensionality, a feature referred to as the curse of dimensionality (Bellman 1957). Acceptable computational times are associated with a dimension of the state vector of 2 or 3, while for larger state vectors, SDP results inapplicable (Loucks et al. 2017). In addition, particularly in large systems, the disturbances are likely to be temporally correlated, and accounting for temporal correlation requires the use of a dynamic stochastic model, which contributes additional state variables and exacerbates the curse of dimensionality. The curse of modelling refers to the SDP requirement that any information included in the SDP framework must be explicitly modelled to predict the one-step-ahead model transition and, ultimately the value function (Tsitsiklis and Van Roy 1996). The implication of the curse of modelling is that no exogenous information can be added to the model unless it is turned into a state variable of a dynamic model (adding to the curse of dimensionality) or a stochastic time-independent disturbance. Finally, the curse of multiple objectives (Powell 2007) is related to those problems where the presence of multiple conflicting objectives requires generating a set of non-dominated alternatives, i.e., a Pareto front. The full set of Pareto-optimal solutions supports a posteriori decision-making by allowing the decision-maker to explore the key alternatives that compose system trade-offs and providing them with a broader context where their preferences can evolve and be exploited opportunistically (Woodruff, Reed, and Simpson, 2013). Most of the DP-family methods rely on single-objective optimisation algorithms. Their application to multi-objective problems requires the use of a scalarisation function to reduce the dimensionality of the objective space to a single-objective problem (Chankong and Haimes, 1983; Reville and McGarity, 1997). The single-objective optimisation is then repeated for every Pareto-optimal point generated by using different scalarisation values (Soncini-Sessa, Weber and Castelletti, 2007). This process can be computationally very intensive in many-objective optimisation problems. Moreover, the Pareto front approximation loses in accuracy given the non-linear relationships between the scalarisation values and the corresponding objectives values.

The three curses of SDP limit its application in complex systems, therefore, over the years, several alternative methods have emerged, seeking to overcome one or more of these curses. Among these approaches, (i) **value-function-based methods** contrast the curse of dimensionality by computing an approximation of the value function (Bertsekas and Tsitsiklis, 1995) that requires a sparser discretisation grid; (ii) **online methods** instead rely on the sequential resolution of multiple open-loop problems defined over a finite receding horizon (Bertsekas, 2005) addressing the curse of modelling. These two approaches, however, still require the estimation of the value function and its optimisation is still carried out as a single-objective problem; (iii) **policy-search-based methods** that make use of a simulation-based optimisation to iteratively improve the operating policies based on the simulation outcome (Marbach and Tsitsiklis, 2001). This latter, generally named Direct Policy Search (DPS) (Rosenstein and Barto 2001), has been recently extended to solve multi-objective problems by using Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithms (MOEAs), resulting in a viable option to address all three curses of SDP (Giuliani et al., 2016).

4.3.1 Evolutionary multi-objective direct policy search

Evolutionary multi-objective direct policy search (EMODPS) replaces the traditional SDP approach based on the computation of the value function with a simulation-based optimisation that directly operates in the policy space. EMODPS first parameterise the operating policy p_θ within a given family of functions and then, explores the parameter space θ seeking the best parameterisation of the operating policy with respect to the expected long-term cost defined by the objectives of the problem, i.e.:

$$p_\theta^* = \arg \min_{p_\theta} J_{p_\theta} \quad s.t. \quad \theta \in \Theta; \quad s_{t+1} = f_t(s_t, u_t, q_{t+1}) \quad (9)$$

where the vector of objective functions' components is described in paragraph 4.1.1.

Finding p_{θ}^* corresponds to finding the best parameters θ^* for the class of policy p_{θ} , measured by the objectives $J_{p_{\theta}}$. A schematisation of the EMODPS algorithm is reported in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Schematisation of the Evolutionary Multi-Objective Direct Policy Search (EMODPS) approach; dashed lines represent the model of the system, and the grey box represents the MOEA algorithm (Giuliani et al., 2016).

Because of the simulation-based nature of EMODPS, the variables domain does not need to be discretised, overcoming at once the curse of dimensionality and the biases introduced by the discretisation of continuous variables (Baxter and Bartlett, 2001). Moreover, it is possible to couple DPS with exogenous information or models, thus avoiding the curse of modelling (Giuliani et al., 2016; Denaro et al., 2017). Finally, the use of MOEAs resolves to curse of multi-objective as EMODPS algorithms allow to produce an approximation of the Pareto front in a single run for up to 10 objectives (Giuliani et al., 2014).

4.3.2 Operating policy optimization

4.3.2.1 Policy structure

EMODPS resolves a problem of parameters optimisation for a given policy structure. It can therefore find, at most, the best possible solution for the chosen class of functions. When the system to be optimised is already operating, it is possible to infer the policy structure from the available data, although the water managers may not have operated at full attainable efficiency. If the system is under construction, neither data nor experience is available, and the policy structure must be guessed a priori based on empirical considerations. The choice of a function with limited flexibility can thus restrict the search to a subspace of policies that, likely, does not contain the optimal one. It is hence advisable to select a very flexible class of functions, depending on a larger number of parameters, to ensure the possibility of approximating the unknown optimal solution of the problem to any desired degree of accuracy. Usually, the selected functions are universal approximating networks (for a review, see Tikk et al., 2003 and references therein). Two widely used non-linear universal approximators are artificial neural networks (ANNs) and radial basis functions (RBFs) (Zoppoli et al., 2002). It has been shown that any continuous function defined on a closed and bounded set can be approximated by three-layered ANNs (Cybenko, 1989; Funahashi, 1989) and three-layered RBFs (Chen and Chen, 1995; Park and Sandberg, 1991).

Although ANNs are more popular in the field of water management than RBFs, a comparative analysis carried out in the Red River basin (Giuliani et al., 2016) shows the general superiority of RBF on ANN for the problem of parameterisation of the operating policy. RBF policies computed for different time horizons consistently score better performances within a more reliable framework, i.e., without requiring any tuning or preconditioning of the policy design process. RBF thus represent an effective, case study-independent option for solving EMODPS problems and are therefore chosen as the universal approximation network for this study.

The RBF policy can be defined as follows:

$$u_t = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \varphi_i(I_t) + a \quad (10)$$

where N is the number of RBFs $\varphi(\cdot)$ and w_i are the weight of the i -th RBF. A single RBF is defined as

$$\varphi_i(I_t) = \exp \left[- \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{[(I_t)_j - c_{j,i}]^2}{b_{j,i}^2} \right] \quad (11)$$

where M is the number of policy inputs I_t and c_i, b_i are the M -dimensional centre and radius vectors of the i -th RBF, respectively. The centres of the RBF must lie within the bounded input space, and the radii must strictly be positives, i.e., using normalised variables, $c_i \in [-1, 1]$ and $b_i \in (0, 1]$. The parameter vector θ is therefore defined as $\theta = [a, c_{i,j}, b_{i,j}, w_i]$ with $i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, M$, and it belongs to \mathbb{R}^{n_θ} , where $n_\theta = N(2M + nu) + 1$.

4.3.2.2 Optimisation algorithm – Borg MOEA

The two main options for the optimisation step of the algorithm (the grey box in Figure 15) are gradient-based methods and global optimisation algorithms, such as MOEAs. Simple parameterisations with few parameters are usually coupled with gradient-based methods, while global optimisation algorithms are preferred when the number of parameters to optimise is high. MOEAs are iterative search algorithms that evolve a Pareto-approximate set of solutions by mimicking the randomised mating, selection, and mutation operations that occur in nature to drive the search for efficient solutions (Coello Coello et al., 2007). MOEAs have been shown to adapt well to multi-objective problems characterised by multi-modality, non-linearity, stochasticity, and discreteness (see Maier et al. 2014 and references therein). MOEAs thus represent a promising alternative to gradient-based optimisation methods in solving complex multi-objective water reservoir problems. In addition, MOEAs were proven to better handle performance uncertainties than gradient-based methods (Busa-Fekete et al., 2014). EMODPS is characterised by a high-dimensional space of policy parameters, and non-linear, multi-objective functions. To perform the optimisation, we use the self-adaptive Borg Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm, which has been shown to be highly robust in solving multi-objective optimal control problems, where it met or exceeded the performance of other state-of-the-art MOEAs (Zatarain Salazar et al., 2016). Borg MOEA differs from traditional evolutionary algorithms because the application of these operators is not bound to a fixed probability of occurrence. Their employment is adaptively adjusted during the course of the optimisation, considering their ability to generate efficient solutions (Hadka and Reed, 2013). Along with the auto-adaptive search, Borg MOEA features other two strategies to contrast the main shortcomings of evolutionary algorithms: overfitting and poor exploration of the whole space when the search is trapped in a local minimum. The first strategy, the so-called ϵ -box dominance archive, divides the optimisation space into hyper-boxes with side-length equal to ϵ . Pareto efficient solutions are searched into each box, ensuring convergence. ϵ -box dominance also supports the second strategy: time continuation. Time continuation ensures a global search of the space by injecting mutated solutions in each ϵ -box. Stagnation in a local minimum is prevented with internal algorithmic operators that detect search stagnation and randomly restart to escape local optima. Borg MOEA has been shown to outperform 9 benchmark evolutionary algorithms in terms of the number of solutions returned, ability to handle many-objective problems, ease-of-use, and overall consistency across a suite of challenging multi-objective problems (Reed et al., 2013).

4.4 Overall structure of the framework

We have now defined all the elements composing the simulation-optimization framework reported in Figure 16. The original drinking water distributed system implemented in Aquator is replicated by a reduced model, which is then integrated into the strategic model of the system. The strategic model is used to compute the performance indicators (irrigation, industrial and drinking deficit, and the drinking water distribution cost). Considering these indicators as objective functions, and evolutionary multi-objective optimization engine derives a set of Pareto efficient policies. This optimization loop is repeated till a pre-defined termination condition is reached.

Finally, to further check consistency of the reduced model, we can simulate the policy identified using the original drinking water distribution system to derive the actual values of the two drinking-related indicators. As said, this

cannot be done in the optimization loop due to the implementation and computational issues. It is worth noting that despite the high accuracy ensured by the surrogate model, it computes aggregated indicators that are representative of the stakeholder’s main interests.

Figure 16: Scheme of the simulation-optimization framework with the possible switch between original and reduced model implementation of the drinking water distribution system.

4.5 Baseline scenario

The scheme reported in Figure 16 remains the same independently of the scenario considered. The elements that define a given scenario are:

- 1) the hydrological flows in input to the system that define the water volumes available;
- 2) the water demands for irrigation, industrial and drinking sector that are used to compute the water deficits;
- 3) eventual unconventional water reuse technologies adopted.

The baseline scenario is a snapshot of the hydro-climatic and socio-economic conditions for the historical decade considered (2010-2019). No unconventional water reuse technologies are currently in use, and this they are not considered in this scenario.

4.5.1 Hydrological flows

The hydrological flows we consider are the inflows to the five water reservoirs (Occhito, Locone, Conza, Pertusillo and Monte Cotugno) and the flows of the two natural springs (Calore and Sele). The inflow time series for the historical period are estimated by inverting the water-balance equation, thus deriving the net inflow (the inflow minus the losses due to evaporation and eventually, to seepage). Net inflow can assume negative values, especially during summertime when, because of the high temperature, evaporation is greater than the flow drained by the hydrological basin. This indirect modelling of the hydrological basins could appear as a coarse simplification of the physical processes, but in fact it allows us not modelling the losses at each time step, a task that always turn out to be hard due to the lack of reliable dataset that includes these variables. The discharge of the two natural springs does not have to be estimated, since direct measurements are available for the historical period here considered.

The time series of the hydrological flows representing the input to the Apulian water system here considered are reported in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Trajectories of the inflow to the reservoirs and flow of the two natural springs for the historical period (2010-2019).

4.5.2 Water demands

In order to compute the water deficits of the irrigation, industrial and drinking sectors, the demands need to be estimated for all the users (i.e., the agricultural and industrial districts, as well as the municipalities and, in general, all the urban settlements). The procedure used to estimate the demands are presented in the Deliverable D4.1, while here it is just summarized.

In our strategic model, we compute the irrigation demand at the reservoir-level. This means that all the demands of the agricultural districts that receive water from a certain reservoir are aggregated in a single value. An agricultural district can rely on different sources (for instance, more than one reservoir, groundwater or external

Figure 18: Current irrigation and industrial water demands.

water sources that are not considered in this study). In this case, only the fraction of water demand that is actually required to each reservoir is considered. To estimate this fraction, the historical mean fraction among sources that provides water to each irrigation district has been considered.

In this way, we can map the water demand of each agricultural district, that are reported in previous studies by the Apulia region (Regione Puglia) and the regional water authority (Autorità di Bacino della Puglia) into a water demand for each reservoir.

For instance, Occhito provides 63% of the water supplied by the Capitanata irrigation district. Consequently, Occhito should satisfy 63% of the estimated agricultural water needs of the same irrigation district. This method has been used to design the agricultural water demand for the Locone reservoirs as well. The situation is more critical for the reservoirs of Monte Cotugno, Pertusillo and Conza since they supply water (also) to some irrigation districts outside Apulia. Therefore, we do not have the same contextual information to undertake the same type of comparison. Accordingly, to estimate the irrigation water demand, historical data provided by the reservoir regulators was used to design an equivalent demand for each reservoir. The resulting irrigation water demands are reported in the top 5 panels of Figure 18. As expected, all the patterns present a similar behaviour with a peak of the water requested during in July/August and a low (or null) demand from November to April.

The situation is relatively straightforward for the industrial sector since there is only one relevant industrial user in our system. Its demand is associated to the Monte Cotugno reservoir and present a constant demand of 0.4 m³/s (see the bottom panel of Figure 18, where small variability is due to the different number of days in each month).

The framework used for the irrigation and industrial users cannot be applied to the drinking sector. In this case, it is not possible to associate a given water demand to each reservoir due to the presence of the water distribution network that allows to transfer relevant volumes across the whole region, even tens of kilometres away from the water source. Downstream of each reservoir (or natural spring) there is a water diversion that conveys the flow into a potable water treatment plant, and from there the water is distributed through the aqueduct to the users. The distribution of the drinking water is thus much trickier than that directed to irrigation and industrial districts. This process, however, is not directly implemented in our strategic model since we use Aquator (or its emulator) to this aim.

Figure 19: Current aggregated drinking demand.

The aggregated demand for the drinking sector is shown in Figure 19. Its pattern is fairly constant within the year, with the main peak in August (historically the summer holiday period in Italy).

4.6 Future climate scenarios

The identification of robust operating policies requires to consider not only historical hydro-meteorological and socio-economic data, but to extend the analysis to a set of possible future scenarios that have to represent the future variability of the processes at hand (in this case, the inflows into the reservoirs and the flows of the two natural springs).

We use the future climate scenarios provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in the fifth Assessment Report (AR5) in 2014, that have become a standard in the field of climate modelling and research in the last years. The IPCC report presents four Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP), each one describing a different climate future depending on the greenhouse gas (GHG) concentration trajectory. The pathways, all of which are considered possible depending on the volume of greenhouse gases emitted in the years to come, are labelled after a possible range of radiative forcing values in the year 2100 (2.6, 4.5, 6, and 8.5 W/m², respectively). For each RCP, it is possible to compute the corresponding increase (with respect to the period from 1850 to 1900) of the global surface temperature, that is expected to exceed 2°C before the end of the 21st century for RCP 6.0 and RCP 8.5, and more likely than not to exceed 2°C for RCP 4.5 (see Figure 20).

Figure 20: Historical values (1900-2005) and future IPCC projections (2005-2100) of the global surface warming under four RCPs.

In our analysis, we consider two RCPs. A moderate scenario represented by RCP 4.5, that is described by the IPCC itself as an intermediate scenario, and an extreme scenario RCP 8.5, generally taken as the basis for worst-case analysis (in the last decade, RCP 8.5 has been thought to be very unlikely, but still possible).

These future climate projections are generated at the global scale and are used as input of global and regional models to generate variables such as temperature and rainfall. Since our strategic model takes as input water flows at the local scale, it is first necessary to downscale the projections of temperature, precipitation, ... from large to local scale, and then to estimate a relationship these variables to the water flows.

4.6.1 Statistical downscaling

The first step is performed using a traditional statistical downscaling method, the quantile mapping (see, for instance, Enayati et al., 2021).

Figure 21: Observation, control before the downscaling and corrected control (after the downscaling) on the control period 2006-2019 for temperature (top) and precipitation (bottom). Pertusillo reservoir is here considered as an example.

Quantile mapping techniques as a bias correction method that is used to remove possible systematic errors in the global circulation models (GCMs) or in the regional circulation model (RCMs). This approach attempts to link the large-scale atmospheric predictor variables (temperature and precipitation) to the local-scale meteorological time series of the corresponding variable (Dibike and Coulibaly, 2005). Quantile mapping aims at finding a transformation that correct the distribution of the large-scale variables so that it becomes as close as possible to the corresponding local-scale variables in the control (historical) period. The outcome of this procedure is reported in Figure 21 for temperature and precipitation in the location of the Pertusillo reservoir.

Once the downscaling transformation is identified on the control period (2006-2019 in our case), it can be applied to correct the bias of the large-scale dataset on future period as well. The application of the quantile mapping correction for Pertusillo (RCP 8.5 is used as a climatic projection) in the future horizon 2020-2100 is reported in Figure 22. The same procedure (identification of the correction transformation on the control period and application of such transformation on the future horizon) has to be performed for every reservoir (or natural spring), meteorological variable, and climatic scenario.

Figure 22: Observation, control before the downscaling and corrected control (after the downscaling) on the future horizon 2020-2100 for temperature (top) and precipitation (bottom). Pertusillo and RCP 8.5 are here considered.

4.6.2 Inflow projections generation

Once the temperature and precipitation projections have been downscaled, it is necessary to estimate the relationship between these two variables to the water flows. Following the same approach of the quantile mapping, the relationship has to be estimated on historical data and then applied to future time series.

This relationship is usually estimated by means of a physically based models, ranging from basic rainfall-runoff model to more complex implementation such as the HBV models, that describe the dynamics of the different processes (such as those related to snow, soil moisture or the routing) through dedicated routines. However, the lack of reliable datasets for the area of interest in terms of temporal coverage and data quality prevents a satisfactory calibration of the parameters. In addition, as we already pointed out, the inflow time series for the historical period are estimated by inverting the water-balance equation, thus deriving the net inflow (inflow minus the losses, such as the evaporation). Net inflow can assume negative values, especially during summertime when evaporation is greater than the flow drained by the hydrological basin, that cannot be directly modelled with HBV models since they require to model the losses with specific sub models.

To directly derive the net inflow from temperature and rainfall, we follow an empirical data-driven approach (specifically the ANNs) instead of the traditional physical one. Differently from the two neural models adopted as operating policy of the system and reduced model of the water distribution network, we are now dealing with a task that present somehow a different structure. The operating policy, for instance, is used to compute the release decision depending on the current storage of the reservoirs. This is a static task since the current state of

the system contains all the information necessary to take the decision. In other words, there is no need of retaining the past states. Similarly, the reduced model of the drinking water distribution system is a static function that reproduces the relationship between the daily discharge of the reservoirs (and of the two natural springs) into the aqueduct, and the drinking water deficit and distribution cost generated for that day. Unlike the two cases discussed above, the value of the net inflow at a given time step, does not depend only on the values of temperature and rainfall at the same time, but also on their previous values. For this reason, a good model of the inflow must keep track of the past input values to produce a suitable estimation of the target variable. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) can do that thanks to their internal memory and are known to be particularly effective in tackling tasks with a sequential/temporal structure compared to traditional feed-forward (memoryless) networks (Han et al., 2004; Chandra and Zhang, 2012), though their training is computationally heavier (Goodfellow et al., 2016).

For this purpose we consider a specific type of recurrent neuron, the LSTM cell (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997). As depicted in Figure 23, each LSTM cell has a two-dimensional state composed of the so-called hidden state, which is also the LSTM's output and corresponds to the state of a standard recurrent neuron and of the cell state, responsible for keeping track of the input's long-term effects. Three gates modulate the information flows: input, output, and forget gates. Each gate's value is the output of a sigmoid in the range from 0 (closed gate) to 1 (open gate). The forget gate enables the LSTM neuron to reset the cell state at appropriate times (when the combination of input and hidden state into the sigmoid is low). Similarly, the input gate decides the extent to which the candidate cell state update (generated by a hyperbolic tangent) affects the cell state, protecting it from irrelevant contributions. The output gate modulates the candidate hidden state (generated by the other hyperbolic tangent) and avoids the negative effect of currently irrelevant memory contents. During training, this gated structure prevents vanishing (or exploding) gradients that generally affect convergence in traditional RNNs.

Figure 23: Diagram of the internal mechanism of an LSTM cell (figure from Sangiorgio et al., 2021).

For each reservoir (or natural spring), an LSTM model is identified on the historical data (from 2010 to 2019). The comparison between target data and LSTM output are reported in Figure 24 (Occhito), Figure 25 (Locone), Figure 26 (Conza), Figure 27 (Pertusillo), Figure 28 (Monte Cotugno), Figure 29 (Calore), and Figure 30 (Sele). In each figure, the left panel presents the net inflow time series trajectory in the 10-year horizon; the right panel compares the cyclostationary cumulative distributions 21-windows moving average. It is worth noting that we are not interested in forecasting with a high accuracy the historical time series, thus reproducing for instance the timing and the exact value of each peak. Our neural model has to be a good synthetic generator, meaning that the more than the timing and punctual values, it has to reproduce the statistical properties of the historical time series. The high similarity between observed and simulated cumulative distributions in all the considered basins ensures the goodness of the neural models identified.

These figures also show that there is a very clear distinction in the dynamics of the inflow into the reservoirs and the flow of the natural springs. These latter have, for almost all the considered years, a relatively constant behaviour (and thus a cumulative distribution quite close to a straight line). The reason is that they are found in karst soils made up of highly permeable limestones, surrounded by highly impermeable clayey soils. Precipitation infiltrates deeply and forms enormous water deposits that are scarcely influenced by seasonal climatic variability. Conversely,

the net inflow to the reservoirs is characterized by a strong periodicity: the derivative of the cumulative distribution is almost flat during summertime (usually characterised by a dry weather) and high slope in wintertime, that is characterized by wetter conditions.

Figure 24: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the inflow to Occhito.

Figure 25: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the inflow to Locone.

Figure 26: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the inflow to Conza.

Figure 27: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the inflow to Pertusillo.

Figure 28: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the inflow to Monte Cotugno.

Figure 29: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the Calore flow.

Figure 30: Comparison between the historical (2010-19) and corresponding simulated trajectories (left) and cumulative annual distribution (right) of the Sele flow.

The quality of the estimate of the flows in the last two cases, the springs, is lower than that obtained for the flows to the reservoirs, in particular in the central years of the considered decade. This is due to the presence of the water table and infiltration phenomena, the dynamics of which would require feeding the LSTM with precipitation measurements in a wider area and which unfortunately are not available.

Once the LSTM models have been identified on the historical period, they can be applied also to the future, considering as input the climate projections that we previously downscaled to the local scale. The historical and projected time series of temperature, rainfall and inflow are presented in Figure 31 (Occhito), Figure 32 (Locone), Figure 33 (Conza), Figure 34 (Pertusillo), Figure 35 (Monte Cotugno), Figure 36 (Calore), and Figure 37 (Sele).

In each figure, the panel in the same column are obtained considering the same climate scenarios (RCP 4.5 on the first column, RCP 8.5 on the second one). Each row is relative to a given variable (temperature, rainfall and inflow respectively). In each panel, there are three cyclostationary trajectories, one for each 10-year horizon: the historical period (2010-19), a mid-term future (2050-59) and a long-term future (2090-99). Note that the data relative to the historical period are the same in both the columns since they are observed values, not climatic projections.

In general, for the various reservoirs, an increase in temperatures is observed as the horizon moves away, which corresponds to a decrease in rainfall and inflows. This is more unambiguous in the case of the second climate scenario.

Figure 31: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to Occhito for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

Figure 32: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to Locone for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

Figure 33: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to Conza for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

Figure 34: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to Pertusillo for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

Figure 35: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to Monte Cotugno for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

Figure 36: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to the Calore springs for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

Figure 37: Temperature, precipitation and inflow relative to the Sele springs for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 (time horizons 2010-19, 2050-59 and 2090-99).

4.7 Future drinking demand

Beyond the variability of the hydro-meteorological conditions due to the climate change, that affects the inflows to the system, it is necessary to consider the future changes of the drinking demand pattern. In a recent study, the Apulian water authority (Autorità Idrica Pugliese, AIP) defines a future pattern that reflects the expected socio-economic changes. The projections are mainly driven by the tourist development, that will strongly increase the drinking water demand on the coastline on the one hand and concentrate the request during summertime (the traditional holiday period in Italy) on the other. The comparison between the current demand (aggregated values for the whole region), used in the baseline, and the future projection by AIP is presented in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Comparison between current (grey area) and future (black area) drinking demand.

Overall, the expected annual growth is in the order of 80.9 Mm³.

4.8 Water reuse technologies

The previous sections show that the water balance in the region will be affected by two concurrent terms. First, a remarkable water volume will be lost as a consequence of the new hydrological regime. Second, the water demand will increase due to the future socio-economic development of the region. The combination of these changes requires to carry out mitigation actions to reduce the pressure on freshwater resources (Cagno et al., 2022). We here consider and implement two strategies for water reuse: wastewater reclamation and reactivation of dismissed wells.

4.8.1 Water reclamation

The first typology of water reuse that we consider is related to water reclamation for irrigation and industrial use. The quantification of the potential water volume to be reclaimed in the Apulia Region, as well as the specific sites where the reclamation technologies can be used in the future are investigated in the Project Ô Deliverable D5.7 (Economic and operational analysis of technology adoption through case studies). We integrate the relevant elements emerged from this analysis in the context of our modelling framework by associating each plant mentioned in the D5.7 to an irrigation or industrial district considered in our model.

Each water reclamation plant is then indirectly implemented as a reduction of corresponding demand. The reduction corresponds to the quantity of water which is provided by water reclamation and thus does not have to be fulfilled with freshwater resources. The comparison between water demand in the present situation versus the reduced demand due to the water reclamation is shown in Figure 39. The percentage water reduction for agriculture is remarkable only for the districts linked to Occhito (31.54 Mm³/year) and Locone (3.94 Mm³/year) reservoirs. In the other irrigation districts, the reduction seems to be negligible if compared to the demand, but actually produces an overall saving of 13.88 Mm³/year. In the industrial district associated to the Monte Cotugno

Figure 39: Comparison between current (grey area) and reduced (black area) irrigation and industrial water demands.

reservoir, the future water demand drops to zero, because the hypothesized water reuses fully satisfy the water requirement.

Table 3: Water reclamation amount for the irrigation and industrial districts associated to each reservoir.

District	Water reuse [l/s]	Water reuse [Mm ³ /year]
Irrigation Occhito	1000	31.54
Irrigation Locone	125	3.94
Irrigation Conza	40	1.26
Irrigation Pertusillo	180	5.68
Irrigation Monte Cotugno	220	6.94
Industrial Monte Cotugno	400	12.61
Total	1.97	61.97

The water reuse relative to each irrigation and industrial district is reported in Table 3, and their sum produces an overall freshwater saving of 61.97 Mm³/year.

4.8.2 Reactivation of dismissed wells

An additional water source that can be used to mitigate the effect of the future hydrological regime as well as the new demand pattern is the reactivation of dismissed wells. Over time, in fact, several wells in highly urbanized areas, near the seacoast or close to industrialized contexts have been abandoned due to groundwater pollution (saltwater intrusion and the percolation of pollutant have been identified as the two major causes of the

Figure 40: Map of the existing wells (blue) and of the 7 newly activated wells (orange). The size of each circle represents is proportional to the well's capacity.

groundwater quality deterioration). In general, these are located near the adductors whose reconnection to the aqueduct grid would require limited investments.

For demonstration purpose, among all those abandoned, we identified seven representative wells shown in orange in the map of Figure 40 where those currently in use are also represented (in blue). Table 4 reports the seven dismissed wells location and the flow that can be potentially derived for each of them.

Table 4: Water flow associated to each dismissed well.

Well location	Flow [l/s]	Flow [Mm³/year]
Cerignola	20	0.63
Andria	20	0.63
Bari	20	0.63
Lecce	20	0.63
Taranto	20	0.63
Parco del Marchese	100	3.15
Opera 3	100	3.15
Total	300	9.45

5 Results

5.1 Experiment design

The system's simulation makes use of a historical scenario defined by:

- agricultural and industrial water demands;
- inflows to the reservoirs and from the natural springs;
- drinking water demand and aqueduct operating costs (required for Aquator simulation).

The considered 10-year simulation horizon covers the period from 01/01/2010 to 31/12/2019 at a daily time step. To avoid numerical issues, we considered a sub-daily integration step of two hours.

As explained in the previous Chapter, the operating policy belongs to the class of non-convex RBF. Due to the high computational effort required by the task, we defined a priori the number of units in the policy hidden layer to 14, following the rule of thumb (number of hidden units, 14 = number of inputs, 7, + number of outputs, 6, + 1) suggested in the literature for complex water system management tasks.

Table 5 reports the optimization setting adopted for the multi-objective search.

Table 5: Borg MOEA optimization setting.

Borg parameter	Numerical value
Number of initial random seeds	10
Number of function evaluations	250,000
Number of optimization variables	298
Number of objectives	4
ϵ values	0.1 (squared irrigation deficit) 0.001 (squared industrial deficit) 0.1 (drinking deficit) 0.5 (AQP distribution cost)

Note that the ϵ values reported in the last row of the table are the dimensions of the ϵ boxes (presented in the previous chapter) along each objective. These values have been set considering the variability range of each objective and performing an accurate trial-and-error analysis.

5.2 Baseline scenario

The core result of the analysis is the Pareto front of Figure 41 using a parallel axes plot representation. It allows to visualize the trade-off between the four considered objectives, all to be minimized: irrigation, industrial, drinking deficits (first, second and third vertical axes) and potable water distribution cost (fourth axis). Note that the utopia point, whose coordinates are the best value that can be obtained for each objective individually, would be a horizontal line linking the lower value of each axis (0 in our rescaled visualization) in the parallel plot. As suggested by its name, this point is not practically reachable due to the trade-off between the objectives, but it serves as a reference point to guide the negotiation between the stakeholders to select a suitable compromise policy.

As expected, the parallel plot shows that the four objectives are highly competing. The trade-off between the three deficits (agricultural, industrial, and drinking) is since the three users would make use of the same water resources coming from shared reservoirs. Due to the water scarcity regime in the region at hand, the water volume available

Figure 41: Graphical representation of the trade-off between the four considered objectives for the baseline scenario. The numerical values of the objectives reported in the parallel plot are rescaled between 0 and 1, corresponding to the extreme values (minimum and maximum) found in the optimization process. All the objectives have to be minimized.

is not sufficient to satisfy all the water demands at the same time, leading to a competitive situation. Consistently, the parallel plot shows that the policies that guarantee a low deficit for one of the water users do not produce satisfying values for the other competing sectors. The trade-off is particularly critical between the two main users in terms of the amount of water demanded: the agricultural districts and the aqueduct. The management policies in green give low values for the drinking deficit but high values for the agricultural deficit (the opposite situation occurs for the policies in red).

The figure shows the same pattern also for the last two axes: drinking deficit can be reduced only by increasing the economic cost related to the water distribution (including pumping, potabilization, ...) because, within certain limits, the lack of surface water can be compensated for by withdrawals from the aquifer, a generally more expensive solution.

Parallel plots allow to visualize the trade-off between an arbitrary number of objectives. However, the interpretation of the results is usually much more critical than in the case of a 2-dimensional plot. To this point, we can rule out the fourth axis of the parallel plot (representing the drinking water distribution cost) since they are charged to urban water users and are thus covered by the bills. It is worth noting that removing the AQP cost at this stage does not mean that we do not consider this dimension of the problem at all. During optimization, if there are two policy that produce the same deficits and different distribution costs, the solution at the minimal cost will be considered as Pareto efficient. To further simplify the visualization, we aggregate the irrigation and industrial water deficit, so that we can map the parallel plot of Figure 41 into the 2-dimensional representation reported in Figure 42.

Beyond the representation of the trade-off, we are also interested in selecting few policies that are significant for the case. For instance, we aim at finding a compromise policy, that leverage the benefits of all the considered sectors (star in Figure 42). To achieve this, we first select all policies that guarantee performance in the top 10% of the consumption deficit band. Among them, we chose the best policy in term of irrigation deficit. Another significant choice for our analysis is the one that considers minimizing the drinking consumption deficit as a priority (diamond in Figure 42). In this case, we first select the policies that guarantees a performance in the top 1% of the range of the drinking deficit, and among them, we chose the best policy in term of irrigation deficit.

Figure 42: 2-dimensional Pareto front for the baseline scenario. The star indicates the compromise policy, while the diamond the top-drinking policy.

The system operated with a specific policy can then be simulated so that we can understand its impact. In the following, we present and discuss the following temporal dynamics obtained when the system is managed with the compromise policy:

- the levels of each reservoir;
- the irrigation and industrial water deficits for each district;
- the drinking water deficit (aggregated for the whole distribution system);
- the potable water distribution cost.

Figure 43 presents the time series of the levels for the five reservoirs for the 10-year horizon between 2010 and 2019.

The Conza reservoir and, partially, Locone, are the only ones with results fully exploited almost every year, with a recurring excursion of the level between the minimum and maximum. The other reservoirs show a more variable pattern, with Occhito reaching its minimum in the years 2012 and 2013. The first of these years is also when, together with 2017, the Pertusillo is fully used. Finally, in the case of Monte Cotugno, the level trajectory clearly reflects the trend in inflows, with two of the last three years of the decade considered being classified as leaner than the others.

Figure 43: Daily time series of the reservoirs' level obtained with the compromise policy of the baseline (time horizon 2010-2019).

Figure 44 reports the annual pattern of the reservoirs' levels. The level of each day of the year has been obtained by averaging the values for that day in the 10-year horizon between 2010 and 2019.

All the reservoirs present the same periodic pattern: the water inflows during wintertime (a period of null agricultural demands and low drinking demand) are stored in the reservoirs reaching high water levels during spring. The combined effect of low inflows and high water demands causes a decrease in the reservoirs' level till October/November. At that point, the levels start increasing again during winter due to the process described above.

Figure 44: Trajectories of the reservoirs' level obtained with the compromise policy of the baseline (cyclo-stationary average for the time horizon 2010-2019).

Figure 45 reports the time series of the irrigation (top 5 panels) and industrial (bottom panel) water deficit referable to each reservoir. The results of the simulation show that a null irrigation water deficit for the entire horizon but the 2019 is obtained only in the case of the Loconne reservoir.

Figure 45: Time series of the irrigation (top five panels) and industrial (bottom panel) water deficits obtained with the compromise policy of the baseline scenario (time horizon 2010-2019). Water demand reported in grey for comparison.

In the considered 10-year time horizon, 2012 and 2017 represent two cases of extremely dry years. The effect of these droughts can be easily spotted in the deficit trajectory of Occhitino and Pertusillo. Their deficit is quite low, with the only exceptions of 2012 (for Occhitino) and 2017 (for Pertusillo) as already pointed out previously. Interestingly, the considered policy seems to be able to distribute the deficit between these two districts using a

sort of coordination mechanism, thanks to the possibility of partially compensating for the availability of water for drinking. In this way, at least partially, it is possible to free up resources for irrigation use.

In general, the irrigation district served by Conza reservoir emerges as the most vulnerable to droughts. Its deficit under the selected operating policy is not negligible even in particularly wet years and is exacerbated in critically dry years (i.e., 2012 and 2017).

Monte Cotugno reservoir is the only one distributing water to all the considered sectors, i.e., irrigation, industrial and potable. The pattern recorded for the industrial deficit is low in the first part of the simulation and worsen starting from 2017. This is even more evident looking at the irrigation deficit: it is almost negligible until 2016, while severe water shortages are registered from the following year.

Figure 46 reports the time series of the drinking water deficit produced on the horizon. It can be noticed that the periodic dynamic is quite constant with respect to one of irrigation and industrial deficits reported in Figure 45. In other words, the policy is able to reduce the effect of exceptionally dry years, exploiting alternative water sources (i.e., the wells).

Figure 46: Time series of the drinking water deficit in the Apulia region (overall value across the whole system) obtained with the compromise policy of the baseline scenario (time horizon 2010-2019). Water demand reported in grey for comparison.

Small variations with respect to the standard periodic behaviour can be seen only in case the overall conditions of the system are consistently different from the average as in 2017.

The limited variations across different years in terms of drinking water deficit reported in Figure 46 are in accordance with the constant trajectory shown in Figure 47 for the annual distribution cost sustained by AQP. The average cost for the considered horizon is about 55 M€ per year.

Exploring the Pareto front of Figure 41, we would be able to find policies that are much more efficient in minimizing the water distribution cost: some of them allow to reduce the cost to less than 30 M€. However, due to the strong

Figure 47: Drinking water distribution cost (annual values) obtained with the compromise policy of the baseline scenario (time horizon 2010-2019).

conflict between drinking deficit and distribution cost, this would lead to an unacceptable drinking deficit.

5.3 Environmental flow effect

The baseline scenario analysed in the previous section is not fully coincided with the historical conditions. For instance, it strictly respects the constraint relative to the Environmental Flow (EF). However, the current management of the reservoirs only respect the EF imposed by the Italian and European legislation in case of water abundance. During water-scarce period, the legislation is not always respected with the aim of reducing the deficit (especially for the drinking section, that is usually prioritized). We thus repeat the optimization for the baseline scenario imposing the respect of the constraint related to EFs, reported in Table 6.

Table 6: Environmental flows required downstream of the 5 considered reservoirs.

Basin	Flow [m ³ /s]	Flow [Mm ³ /year]
Occhito	1.78	56.14
Locone	0.07	2.10
Conza	0.05	1.54
Pertusillo	0.75	23.65
Monte Cotugno	0.53	16.60

Figure 48 shows the comparison between the Pareto front of the baseline scenario with the constraint on the EF (same as the one of Figure 42), and the corresponding front obtained not considering the EFs.

Figure 48: Pareto front for the baseline scenario with (light blue) and without (yellow) respecting the EF constraints.

Not considering the EF constraints, a relevant water volume becomes available and is used to satisfy the water demands of the three considered sectors. The pareto front thus moves down-left, producing a better performance for both the objectives, and the shape of the yellow front (always below 0.5 (m³/s)² for the irrigation and industrial squared deficit) indicates that the trade-off between the drinking sector and the other users is strongly reduced with respect to the baseline (light blue front).

5.4 Future climate scenarios

As said, the future climate has a key role in our analysis, since it drives the changes in the hydro-meteorological regimes, and thus the water availability. In our analysis, we consider a moderate (RCP 4.5) and an extreme (RCP 8.5) climate scenario and two future period (2050-59 and 2090-99).

First, we examine the combined effect of future climate and of the respect (or not) of the constraint related to the EFs. For the sake of simplicity, we report the results only for RCP 8.5 in the mid-term horizon (2050-59), while all the combinations of RCP and period will be considered in the following.

Figure 49: Pareto front for the baseline scenario with (light blue) and without (yellow) respecting the EF constraints, and for RCP 8.5 (2050-2059) with (blue) and without (orange) EF.

Figure 49 shows the comparison between the Pareto fronts of the baseline scenario and for RCP 8.5 in the mid-term period, in both the cases with and without the application of EFs. The decrease of water availability due to the climate change will dramatically affect all the sectors (see, for instance, the comparison between the yellow and orange fronts). The situation becomes even worse when considering the EFs following the legislation (compare the orange front with the blue one): the front moves up-right, and its points are widely spread meaning that the conflict between sectors is strongly exacerbated.

As already done for the baseline, for each scenario, we consider a compromise solution that balances the trade-off between the objectives and a top-drinking policy that prioritizes the drinking sector (minimizing its deficit). The annual water deficit obtained with a compromise policy are reported in Figure 50 (irrigation and industrial sectors in the top panel, drinking sector in the bottom one). For instance, under current climatic conditions, the drinking deficit grows from 34.7 Mm³/year to 47.3 Mm³/year due to the imposition of EF constraints. The combined effect of EF and future climate further increases the deficit to 71.8 Mm³/year. When considering the top-drinking policies, the same analysis can be done (see Figure 51). The drinking deficit in the situation closer to the current conditions (baseline without EF) is 22.0 Mm³/year and is expected to become 56.4 Mm³/year (more than doubled, +156%) due to the climatic and legislative variations.

Figure 50: Annual deficit for compromise policies for the baseline scenario with (light blue) and without (yellow) respecting the EF constraints, and for RCP 8.5 (2050-2059) with (blue) and without (orange) EF.

Figure 51: Annual deficit for top-drinking policies for the baseline scenario with (light blue) and without (yellow) respecting the EF constraints, and for RCP 8.5 (2050-2059) with (blue) and without (orange) EF.

5.5 Future drinking demand

In the previous section, we quantified the effect of EF constraint, that are not fully respected in the current management. However, following the European legislation, EFs will have to be considered in the future (they should have already been considered). We thus decide to consider EF in our analysis from now on.

The combined effect of the future pattern of the drinking demand and climate conditions is represented in Figure 52.

Figure 52: Pareto front for the baseline scenario (light blue circles) and for the four future scenarios that combines projections of climatic regimes and drinking demand pattern. Dark red fronts indicate mid-term future (2050-2059), dark red fronts the long-term future (2090-2099). Squares represent RCP 4.5 while triangles RCP 8.5.

The deterioration with respect to the front obtained in the baseline is quite evident along both the axis. Interestingly, three of the four Pareto fronts (RCP 4.5 2050-2059, RCP 4.5 2090-2099, RCP 8.5 2050-2059) are almost overlapped. This is somehow in accordance with the IPCC projections of global surface warming (Figure 20), that estimate a temperature increase between 1.5°C and 2°C for RCP 4.5 as well as for RCP 8.5 (but in the mid-term, say before 2060). Conversely, the temperature increase is expected to be more than 4°C for RCP 8.5 at the end of the century. This latter thus represents a situation of extremely critical climate change that can be observed also in Figure 52.

To give an idea of the magnitude of estimated changes, we can consider the drinking extreme of the fronts. The drinking deficit grows from 31.4 Mm³/year (corresponding to a constant deficit over a decade equal to 1 m³/s) to around 150 Mm³/year (4.5 m³/s) under the more conservative scenarios and to around 200 Mm³/year (6 m³/s) in the case of the more severe scenario (the period 2090-2099 considering the RCP 8.5). This latter is a really huge deficit, considering that it is about 4 times that estimated under current conditions.

5.6 Water reuse technology

The situation obtained under future scenarios is extremely critical, and would cause remarkable environmental, economic and social issues. In this context, it is fundamental to be able to quantify the effect of water reuse

Figure 53: Pareto front for the baseline (light blue circles) and future scenarios. Dark fronts indicate mid-term future (2050-2059), dark fronts the long-term future (2090-2099). Squares represent RCP 4.5 while triangles RCP 8.5. The color of the front indicates the implementation (green) or not (red) of water reuse technologies.

technologies, that can help mitigating the combined effects of climate change and of the new drinking demand pattern.

Figure 53 presents the Pareto fronts obtained with the implementation of non-conventional water reuse technologies (green tones). The comparison between these fronts and the corresponding ones obtained without water reuse (in red) allows to estimate the impact of these water loops.

Even if the situation is remarkably improved, the effect of water reuse implementation is far from entirely closing the gap with the baseline. This means that the specific mitigation actions here adopted are not sufficient and that it is necessary to further promote the spread of reuse technologies. The deficit estimated in the worst case (the decade 2090-2099 considering RCP 8.5) would be reduced by about 10% only, for example.

To give an overview of the annual deficit in the different sectors, we include two bar plots, for compromise policies (Figure 54) and for top-drinking policies (Figure 55).

Figure 54: Annual deficit for compromise policies for the baseline scenario and future scenarios.

Figure 55: Annual deficit for top-drinking policies for the baseline and future scenarios.

5.7 Vulnerability assessment

The framework developed does not limit the analysis to indicators aggregated at the regional scale but can be used also to assess the vulnerability of each specific sector and, even more in detail, of each district obviously considering

Figure 56: Time series of the irrigation, industrial and drinking deficits obtained with the compromise policy for RCP 8.5 in the decade 2050-2059. Water demand reported in grey for comparison.

only the part irrigated by the waters attributable to the investigated reservoirs.

Figure 56 reports the times series of the water deficits of all the agricultural and industrial districts, and of the drinking sector for RCP 8.5 in the decade 2050-2059 using compromise operating policies. Comparing this figure to Figure 45 (trajectories irrigation and industrial deficits for the baseline), it is possible to isolate the effect caused by the climatic and socio-economic variability as well as the impact of the considered water loops.

In the baseline scenario, irrigation deficits are almost null for Pertusillo, Monte Cotugno and Locone (with the exception of 2019). The deficit for the districts associated to Occhito and Conza are quite limited, but their occurrence suggests that these two districts are vulnerable under the current conditions, and thus will probably even more exposed to water shortages in the future. The robustness analysis allows us quantifying the volume associated to these shortages under future conditions. As shown in Figure 56 (first five rows of the first column), the deficits remain substantially the same for Locone, Pertusillo and Monte Cotugno, and a limited increment affects the Conza district. Conversely, the Occhito irrigation district is strongly affected by the future conditions (for instance, in 2056 there is a complete failure of the irrigation system), and thus represent the more vulnerable site of the entire water system. The water reuse actions considered do not substantially modify the situation. Conza and, especially, Occhito remain the two more critical reservoirs from the irrigation point of view. Additional water loops and other infrastructures should thus consider these two districts fed by these reservoirs with a high priority. Considering the industrial sector, the deficit is substantially negligible in the baseline scenario (bottom panel of Figure 45). Under RCP 8.5 with future drinking demand, remarkable water deficits come out during summertime (last but one row, first column of Figure 56), when the competition for water resources is exacerbated by the peaks of the irrigation demands. The implementation of water loops in the industrial district eliminates the corresponding deficit (last but one row, second column of Figure 56) since this demand is expected to fully satisfy by the use of unconventional water resources.

Drinking is the more vulnerable sector among those considered, since it is not possible to reduce its deficit to zero, even when considering the scenario with the high amount of water available (baseline without the respect of EFs) as it is shown in Figure 48.

Figure 46 shows that in the baseline scenario the deficit is close to zero only for short period during spring and fall, while it frequently exceeds 10 Mm³/month in August, the month with the higher competition for the water resources due to the drinking and irrigation demand peaks. The effect of climatic (RCP8.5) and socio-economic (new drinking water demand pattern) changes in the period 2050-2059 (last row, first column of Figure 56) is apparent in the peaks, that are around 25 Mm³/month for each year of the decade (more than twice the value reached under the baseline scenario). Moreover, the minimum annual value grows from the almost null value of the baseline to around 8 Mm³/month, meaning that the current water sources that supply water to the aqueduct will have to be considerably integrated by other sources in the future. The implementation of water reuse technologies (the effect of on the drinking sector is mainly due to the reactivation of seven wells currently dismissed) generates an average drop of the drinking deficit of 1.5 Mm³/month, that represents a relevant amount but only allows to mitigate a small fraction of the deficit generated by the mutated climatic and socio-economic regimes, similarly to what happen in some irrigation districts.

An intrasectorial vulnerability assessment as the one here reported for the agricultural sector can also be repeated for the drinking sector. The only difference with respect to irrigation is that the simulation has to be performed using the complete Aquator implementation that computes the deficit for each end used in a distributed fashion, instead of the reduced-order model (which conversely relies on the aggregated indicators).

Discussion and conclusion

We extend the analysis that has been performed for the baseline scenario to derive a number of operating policies that can robustly deal with future scenarios. In the proposed framework, each scenario is characterized by:

- time horizon;
- environmental flow constraints, that defines the legislative aspects of the scenario;
- inflow time series, that defines the hydro-meteorological aspects of the scenario;
- drinking, irrigation and industrial water demand, that characterizes the socio-economic aspects of the scenario;
- water reuse implementation, that characterizes the technological aspects of the scenario.

The analysis focuses on the interesting combination of these factors and allows us quantifying the consequences of hydrologic regimes caused by climate change, the effects of future patterns of drinking demand driven by the socio-economic development of the region, and the impacts of water reuse technologies implementation.

The proposed framework is based on EMODPS and nests the simulation model into an optimization tool, namely a genetic algorithm, that allows to identify efficient operation policies for managing the whole system. In the current implementation, the policy is identified in the hypothesis that a single water authority can coordinate the water releases from all the storage to reach a compromise solution synthetizing the competing need of the different users. However, this hypothesis somehow represents an ideal situation that does not fully coincide with reality. Indeed, at the beginning of each irrigation season, a negotiation takes place between stakeholders and water authorities to coordinate the reservoirs' operations so that a reasonable compromise can be reached.

The results show that the combined effect of climate and socio-economic changes will dramatically affect the Apulia water system, leading to a situation characterized by an unsustainable pressure on the freshwater resources. In addition, the respect of the constraints related to the environmental flows will further reduce the operation space. The future water deficit is thus expected to increase in the mid-term (2050-2059) and in the long-term (2090-2099), especially when considering RCP 8.5 as climate scenario.

Even if the situation is remarkably improved, the effect of water reuse implementation is far from entirely closing the gap with the current situation. This means that the specific mitigation actions here adopted are not sufficient and that it is necessary to further promote the spread of reuse technologies.

The vulnerability assessment analysis highlights the most critical point of the system. The drinking sector seems to be the more vulnerable and will require consistent infrastructural projects to mitigate the climatic (and socio-economic) changes ongoing. A critical situation is spotted also in the irrigation districts associated to the Occhito and, to a lesser extent, Conza reservoirs. The industrial sector, on the other hand, is less vulnerable than the others, provided that the water reclamation plant considered in our analysis will be put in place.

The methodology here presented can be used to evaluate the impacts of water loops and its technological improvements on different stakeholders and sectors. This is a remarkable improvement with respect to the state of the art that usually limit the analysis to the technical parameters of a given technology (e.g., efficiency, durability, maintenance costs, energy consumption), but without being able to evaluate the impacts on the final users and at the water-system scale. Furthermore, the presented framework is portable, meaning that it can be applied to other case studies independently of their complexity. In case complex elements are present, they can be efficiently including them in the framework by identifying its reduced model, such as we have done for the drinking water distribution network.

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